

Meaning and content in a literary text

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Abstract: This article explores the meaning and style of the work of art and some of the important features of conveying the work of art to the reader. In addition, the purpose of the expression of artistic texts, the aesthetic function of each type, which gives the content of the work, is highlighted. In order to increase students' interest in fiction, the author discusses aspects that need to be addressed.

Keywords: literary text, word, scientific literature, idea, linguistics, media, lexical features, author

For many years, there has been a search for the study of literary text, its analysis, and how to create it. But the question that often arises is, "What is a literary text and how is its meaning determined?"

A literary text has a specific aesthetic purpose in order to engage the reader of the language of the person using that particular literary language. The author of the literature uses the most appropriate words to express his thoughts in a clear style and according to a certain methodological criterion, and helps the reader to understand everything correctly and to understand what the content is organized. The features of a literary text are many and varied, and the feature of a literary text is the creation of a work of art, the purpose of which is artistic, not practical.

The meaning and content of the literary text beautifies the mind, and the essence contained in it is pleasing to the reader's imagination, helping to fully penetrate the text. Content is a very important part and a set of modified elements that represent things as such. The content of the form represents the internal structure of the mode of existence. In fact, in the objective world, there is no pure content or form that is not related to things and events. Just as meaning is always expressed in a certain way, so meaning

has its own form. Meaning and content must be compatible, and if they do not match, a conflict may arise. This conflict is resolved by replacing the meaning and content with another one. In literature, meaning and content are two interdependent aspects of a work, with content being central.

The study of meaning and content in a literary text began in the eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries with a differentiated study. But meaning and content are one, because the meaning of a work, when combined with the content, can express its form. A true work of art is a combination of meaning and content and requires a whole.

The meaning and content of a literary text influences the artistic style. The literary text is rich in many expressive features, including metaphors, imitations, allegories, and so on. Using these tools, the author creates an image of what is being discussed in the play. The meaning and content of a literary text is highly emotional and engaging, and the author can use it to convey his or her feelings, as well as to help the reader express those feelings. For example, using visual aids, the author can connect the mood of a picture of the whole world. However, the mood expressed in this way can't be seen in scientific articles and business journals. From this, we can see how important the meaning and content of the literary text is in creating a high level of emotion in the students. The literary text is based on the author's idea and has its main content.

It is commendable that the most important part of the reforms being carried out in our country is the issue of science, because every research in science is related to the future of our country. The path of opportunities created for scientists, in particular, is to bring the Uzbek literature to the level of world literature, to change styles, to serve the growth of science and thinking among the population. This, in turn, affects the meaning and content of the literary text in the works. In addition, it paves the way for the formation of various new scientific methods in our national literature.

Any text is complex in structure and content, it is an example of oral and written creation. The term text is interpreted differently in the scientific literature. In today's linguistics, text is interpreted as a separate major unit of language and the main object of the field called textual linguistics. It is said that the study of a text must be

distinguished from the wording and the sentence, and that the text has its own categories and laws. E. Kilichev, one of the well-known linguists, describes the text as follows: Literary text differs from other types of text by its lexical and grammatical features, artistic expressiveness.

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